

Clustering-based Filtering of Big Data to improve Forecasting Effectiveness and Efficiency

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Abstract. New challenges arise with the upsurge of a Big Data era. Huge volumes of data, from the most varied natures, gathered from different sources, collected in different timings, often with high associated uncertainty, make the decision-making process a harsher task. Current methods are not ready to deal with characteristics of the new problems. This paper proposes a novel data selection methodology that filters big volumes of data, so that only the most correlated information is used in the decision-making process in each given context. The proposed methodology uses a clustering algorithm, which creates sub-groups of data according to their correlation. These groups are then used to feed a forecasting process that uses the relevant data for each situation, while discarding data that is not expected to contribute to improving the forecasting results. In this way, a faster, less computationally demanding, and effective forecasting is enabled. A case study is presented, considering the application of the proposed methodology to the filtering of electricity market data used by forecasting approaches. Results show that the data selection increases the forecasting effectiveness of forecasting methods, as well as the computational efficiency of the forecasts, by using less yet more adequate data.

1 Introduction

The 21st century economy produces a constant stream of data that is being monitored and analysed. Social interactions, mobile devices, facilities, equipment, R&D, simulations, and physical infrastructure all contribute to the flow. In aggregate, this is what is called Big Data. Right from its emergence, Big Data technology and services market has grown from \$3.2 billion in 2010 to \$16.9 billion in 2015. This represents a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 39.4% or about seven times that of the overall information and communication technology (ICT) market. By 2020 this market is estimated at \$138.62 billion, with an expected CAGR of 10.6% for the period 2020-2025 [1]. Big Data involves new generation technologies and architectures with the aim of extracting value from huge amounts of a wide variety of data, involving data capture, storage, analysis, visualization and knowledge discovery. Nowadays, data sets are growing up in size because they are increasingly being gathered by a several kind of sensors, devices and applications, such as, software logs, cameras, microphones, radio-frequency identification readers, wireless sensor networks, etc. Such useful information that the data may disclose, can provide competitive advantages over rival

organizations and result in business benefits, such as more effective marketing and increased revenue. These trends are also "democratizing" use of data analytics. The type of analytics that used to be only available to the biggest companies in the world can now be done by smaller companies. In order to mine hidden insights from data, enterprises have started leveraging these Big Data systems. An important aspect is that the analysis of large amounts of data may intensify the inferential power of algorithms that have shown to be successful on modest-sized data sets. The real challenge is to develop and increase the theoretical principles needed to scale inference and learning algorithms to massive scale [2]. On the other hand, massive data analysis may amplify the error rates that are part of any inferential algorithm. Thus, the challenge is to control such errors even in the face of the heterogeneity and uncontrolled sampling processes underlying in many large data sets [3].

This paper proposes an innovative data selection methodology that chooses the most appropriate data to be used by forecasting methods. The data filtering process searches for correlations in data, so that only the most relevant data is used in each context. This way the use of data is adapted to each distinct situation, improving the forecasting process by reducing the variability of the used data. The data filtering process also provides its contribution by reducing the forecasting execution time by using less, but more adequate data, in the training process. In this way, efficient contextual services are enabled. The proposed methodology is based on a clustering process application to data with an automatic evaluation. With this, training data for forecasting methods can be chosen automatically according to the relevance and correlation of data for each given problem, preventing the use of excessive and ambiguous data; and also preventing an over-filtering of data that often comes from using only small amounts of highly correlated data while discarding information that could be relevant but whose value is not easily perceived.

After this introductory section, section 2 presents the factory of the future project, in which this work is framed. Section 3 presents the proposed methodology, including the clustering process and the evaluation procedure. Some experimental findings are presented in section 4, where results from the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) to forecast electricity market prices are compared when using the proposed methodology and when not using it. Finally, section 5 presents the conclusions and contributions of the presented work.

2 Continental Factory of the Future

With the advances of worldwide technological infrastructure, both in terms of software and equipment, it is becoming possible to achieve levels of automation and advanced decision making that were unthinkable in the past. Project Continental Factory of the Future [4] is developing new solutions towards the modernization of factories activities. These include relevant aspects that include the operation, maintenance, stock management, social aspects, and also energy efficiency and management.

Such improvement requires dealing with large amounts of real data from distinct sources and natures, which includes, as depicted by Figure 1, data from the factory itself

(data gathered from sensors, measured data and data from the internal management software systems) but also contextual data (e.g. weather data, electricity prices data among many others). It is, therefore, crucial that advanced models are developed to enable analyzing and processing these different data in a way that the relevant data in each moment can be identified and afterwards used by the diverse contextual services that provide support to the factory activities, e.g. for distributed product testing [5].

Figure 1. Contextual data handling

In this specific work we are addressing the filtering of data related to electricity market prices as the way to enable improved forecasting of market prices as a contextual service. This process is described in section 3.

3 Proposed Methodology

Large amounts of data from distinct natures with high associated variety are, nowadays, essential for the decision making process in the most diverse fields. Dealing with the so called Big Data brings an urgent need to manage all these data appropriately [6], in acceptable time frames, depending on each scope of application. Hence, data must be used wisely, since not all available data are necessary (or even useful) for specific decision making tasks. The need to filter and use the most appropriate data

(most correlated, which present the bigger potential gain of information for solving each specific problem) becomes, therefore, essential.

Simple yet fast methods, which do not degrade the computational demand of the decision making methods themselves, are most likely to present good results in a Big Data scope. As Big Data is often associated to Big Gaps in Data, complex methods are not able to perform well, nor bring the necessary added value. Moreover, the execution time that is often required by complex methods to treat data before data are used by the decision support methods, is impracticable when dealing with large volumes of data, especially when fast responses are required.

The methodology proposed in this paper enables filtering the available data, with the aim of filtering the most significant data, so that it can be used by forecasting methods. This work accomplishes this goal by applying a clustering approach to divide the available data into different groups according to their similarity and correlation. The data clusters are then assessed, in order to guarantee the achievement of a suitable balance between the number of clusters and the data variability associated to this clustering process. This enables using the smaller possible number of clusters that allows the maximum data separation (least variability of data). When using a large number of clusters, the available data to train the forecasting methods decreases significantly. This causes a decrease in the effectiveness of the forecasting process. Alternatively, a low number of clusters leads to a very small separation of data, and to a consequent increase in the data variability. A suitable balance between the number of clusters and the associated variability is thereby crucial, aiming at reaching the smaller number of data clusters that results in the higher gain in terms of data variability reduction. The proposed methodology process is presented in Figure 2.

From Figure 2 it is visible that data that is gathered from multiple sources, and then integrated into a common data base originates a Big Data collection, with high associated variability. This raw data is, therefore, analysed by the proposed methodology, where a clustering process is applied. The clustering results are evaluated so that the balance between the number of data sub-groups and the gain in variability reduction can be optimized. The filtered data resulting from the data sub-group that contains the information most related to each distinct problem is finally used by the forecasting methodologies, so that an adequate forecast, using only the necessary data can be performed.

Figure 2. Overview of the proposed methodology

The clustering model used in this work is the well-known K-Means algorithm [7], which enables separating data into different groups, each one containing samples with high similarity among each other but with big differences between different clusters. K-Means contemplates a set of n observations (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) , in which each is a d -dimensional real vector. The clustering process partitions the n observations into k ($\leq n$) clusters $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$ so that the Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WCSS) is minimized.

In order to assess the quality of the clustering process, the Mean Index Adequacy (MIA) and Clustering Dispersion Indicator (CDI) are used [8].

4 Experimental findings

The case study presented in this section has the goal of demonstrating the application of the proposed methodology to the problem of electricity market prices forecasting. With this objective, a data base containing real data from the Iberian electricity market operator – MIBEL [9] is used. These data are collected in real time by an automatic data extraction tool, which has been presented in [10]. This tool is connected to the websites of several electricity market operators, and extracts all kinds of data related to electricity markets, as they are made available. This means that data from diverse natures is constantly being gathered, in different timings, and added to the already stored data.

These experiments regard electricity market prices forecast considering both the forecasting accuracy and execution time. The forecasting models that are used are:

The proposed methodology is applied to the log of historic market prices, with the objective of filtering the data that will be used by an ANN – described in [11], and SVM – described in [12] in forecasting process. The used data set contains hourly electricity market prices from MIBEL ranging from January 2008 onwards (until September 2014). Figure 3 shows the clustering evaluation using MIA and CDI.

Figure 3. MIA and CDI clustering evaluation for different numbers of clusters

From Figure 3 three different “elbows“, where data variance stabilizes, are clearly identified: using 4 clusters, 10 clusters, and 15 clusters. These three points present the transition points in which the variance decrease stabilizes; i.e. they represent the alternative ideal numbers of clusters that show the least variance between data, using the least number of data sub-groups.

Figure 4 presents the results of the clustering process using: a) 4 clusters, b) 10 clusters, and c) 15 clusters. These results show visually how data has been grouped, using a small exemplification group of 31 days, each containing 24 hourly periods. These 31 days are referent to the 31 days of January, 2014.

From Figure 4 it is visible that the clustering process is able to group data according to its similarity. In Figure 4 a) it is visible a clear separation between the peak periods (where the market price is higher, namely hours 20 and 21); off-peak periods, between hours 2 and 7; mid-valued price periods, between hours 8 and 18, and hours 1 and 24; and near-peak periods, namely hours 19, 22 and 23. Using 10 and 15 clusters, as seen in Figure 4 b) and Figure 4 c) a more exhaustive separation is achieved, where the tendency of market prices in all days is captured. As mentioned before, the forecasting methodologies, using the proposed methodology, only consider data of each sub-group when performing a forecast for a corresponding hour. E.g. if performing a forecast for the electricity market price of hour 21, when using 4 clusters, only data referent to the historic market prices in hours 20 and 21 are considered; when considering 10 or 15 clusters, only data from previous days in hour 21 are considered. Table 1 presents a comparison of the average Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and the execution time achieved by the forecasting process using the ANN and the SVM with and without the use of the proposed methodology, for a total of 2160 day-ahead forecasts (considering the individual forecast of each of the 24 hours of 90 days).

Figure 4 Data grouping resulting from the clustering process using: a) 4 clusters, b) 10 clusters, c) 15 clusters

Table 1. ANN and SVM MAPE forecast error (%) and execution time (m.s.)

	ANN		SVM	
	MAPE	time	MAPE	time
Without proposed model	0,096	18314	0,095	5107
With proposed model (4 clusters)	0,088	13701	0,089	4941

Table 1 shows that the forecast error is smaller when using the proposed methodology for both ANN and SVM. It is also visible that the execution time when using the proposed methodology is lower for both forecasting models, benefiting from the use of less, but more adequate data, in the training process.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents a data selection methodology with the objective of filtering data before its use by complementary forecasting methodologies. The data filtering process aims at searching for correlations in data, so that only the most relevant data is used in each context; this way adapting the use of data to each distinct situation, with the intention of improving the forecasting process by reducing the variability of data. Additionally, the aim is also placed on reducing the forecasting execution time by using less, but more adequate data, in the training process.

Results have shown an increase of the forecasting efficiency through the decrease of the forecasting execution time. Besides resulting in an increase of computational efficiency, the proposed methodology also provides an increase of forecasting effectiveness, as demonstrated in the experimental findings section, showing that an adequate data selection according to the requirements of each distinct situation is able to improve the forecasting quality by reducing the amount of redundant data, hence focusing only on the data that matters the most in each context.

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